

PREPARATION AND STUDY OF MICROSTRUCTURE OF YTTRIA AND CERIA STABILIZED TETRAGONAL ZIRCONIA POLYCRYSTALS FOR DENTAL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The overall aim of this work was the preparation of two different zirconia ceramics material stabilized in their tetragonal form by 3mol% of Yttria (3Y-TZP) and 12mol% of Cerria (12Ce-TZP), study the different sintering paramaters and their influence of the phase transformation, density and microstructure. 3Y-TZP and 12Ce-TZP powders after freeze granulation an freeze drying by 48h were subjected for unaxial pressing with pressure of 50MPa and then for Cold Isostatic pressing with pressure of 350MPa. Prepared materials were sintered in four different temperatures 1300°C, 1400°C, 1450°C and 1500°C with the dwell time 2h. After sintering the phase and microstructure analysis were carried out. The aim of the experiments is to select the best sintering method in order to obtain the finest

microstructure of prepared Y-TZP and Ce-TZP ceramics and to evaluate their resistance for Low Temperature Degradation (LTD) and corrosion tests in acetic environment.

Keywords: Y-TZP, Ce-TZP, microstructure, sintering

INTRODUCTION

The excellent mechanical properties of zirconia-based materials combined with their superior aesthetics and biocompatibility characteristics have encouraged their application as bioceramics, particularly in the dental field. Yttria stabilized zirconia ceramics (Y-TZP) compared to other bio ceramics is characterized by its superior flexural strength and high fracture toughness, thus becoming very interesting materials for dental applications. In addition, it can be accurately processed to complex geometries using CAD-CAM Technologies or low pressure-injection moulding. However, this ceramic can undergo Low Temperature Degradation (LTD) which refers to a spontaneous zirconia phase transformation from the metastable tetragonal (t) phase to the stable monoclinic (m) [1] that can cause micro-cracking, loss of strength, roughness increase and the device destruction. [2]. For this reason, research focused on ceria-stabilized zirconia (Ce-TZP) is gaining a lot of interest. Our latest studies on two commercial Y-TZP dental ceramics and Ce-TZP ceramics prepared by MATEIS laboratory of Insa Lyon have shown that Ce-TZP is the most resistant for LTD. However, in the case of Y-TZP we have subjected two materials with similar composition but with different microstructure. Y-TZP ceramics with the finest grain-size was much less vulnerable for LTD. The presence of grain size bigger than $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ will make the zirconia microstructure more sensitive to LTD. It is very necessary to find out the rules controlling the grain size, phase content and sintered density. Low density, especially the presence of open porosity, offers to water molecules an easy access to the bulk of the material [3].

The aim of this our study is to select the best sintering method in order to obtain the finest microstructure of prepared 3Y-TZP and 12Ce-TZP ceramics. Our next step will be the evaluation of their resistance for Low Temperature Degradation (LTD) and corrosion tests in acidic environment.

EXPERIMENTAL

Powders using in this experiment, 3 mol% Yttria stabilized zirconia and 12 mol% Cerria stabilized zirconia were prepared using hydrothermal technique. The precursors were zirconium oxychloride ($\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$), 96% BDH Chemicals Ltd, England; Yttrium oxide (Y_2O_3), 99.9%, Fluka AG; Cerium (III) chloride hydrate ($\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$), Sigma Chemicals Co. 3Y-TZP and 12Ce-TZP powders after being freeze granulate and freeze dried were pressed uniaxially ($p=50 \text{ MPa}$) into disc compacts and then Cold Isostatic Pressed with pressure of 350MPa, dwell time: 3min, drain time: 50s and the slow decompression. Such prepared materials were burning out in $T_1 = 400^\circ\text{C}$ (heating rate: 10°C/h), after temperature were increased to $T_2 = 800^\circ\text{C}$ (heating rate: 120°C/h and dwell time: 30min). Sintering experiments were performed at four different temperatures 1300°C , 1400°C , 1450°C , 1500°C in air with 2 h soaking time. Scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM-7600

F/EDS/WDS/EBS) was performed to observe the microstructures of the sintered samples, and the average grain size was estimated from the SEM micrographs by the intercept method. X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out using X-ray diffractometer, Panalytical Empyrean DY1098 to measure the phase content. The phase content were evaluated by Highscore HighScore Plus (v. 3.0.4.) with the COD crystallographic open database COD 2017.

RESULTS

The SEM micrographs of sintered in choosed temperatures, polished and thermally etched samples are shown below respectively for 3Y-TZP ceramics (fig 1.) and 12Ce-TZP ceramics (fig 2.). In the case of 3Y-TZP ceramics the high dense microstructure is obtained in 1450°C with the measured average grain sizes of 382 nm. 3Y-TZP ceramics sintered in 1450°C is characterized by fine-grained microstructure (fig. 1 c). The grains are isometric in shape. There is no visible porosity. However with the increasing of the sintering temperature to 1500°C the bigger grains with the average size of 487 nm were obtained.

*Fig 1. SEM micrographs - microstructure of a 3Y-TZP with different sintering temperatures:
a) 1450°C b) 1500°C*

In 12Ce-TZP ceramics, the grain boundaries were clearly visible in the highest sintering temperature (fig 2. d). However, the grain size was not uniform and was higher than 1000nm. X-ray diffraction analysis have shown that monoclinic phase occurred only after polishing treatment in 3Y-TZP ceramic, sintered in $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fig 2. SEM micrographs - microstructure of a 12Ce-TZP with different sintering temperatures: a) 1300°C b) 1400°C c) 1450°C d) 1500°C,

CONCLUSIONS

In order to obtain the finest microstructure of prepared Y-TZP and Ce-TZP the sintering in 1450°C and 1500°C for both materials were selected. Y-TZP ceramics have much more fine-grained microstructure than Ce-TZP. It is thus very difficult to obtain a fine-grained, fully dense Ce-TZP. Chevalier et. al [4] reported that standard Ce-TZP achieve more extensive grain coarsening after sintering in comparison to Y-TZP. The mobility of grain boundaries is much higher in Ce-TZP than in Y-TZP. The experimental data will be expands for next evaluatenig resistance for Low Temperature Degradation (LTD) and corrosion tests in acetic environment the Y-TZP for both material sintered with selected method.

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